

Clonal Propagation of *Anogeissus Acuminata* (Roxb. Ex DC.) Wall. Ex Guill. & Perr. for Conservation and Genetic Improvement

Sanjay Singh

ICFRE-Eco Rehabilitation Centre, Prayagraj, India

ABSTRACT: This research explores the standardization of clonal propagation *Anogeissus acuminata* (Phasi), a multipurpose deciduous tree with medicinal and timber value. Given the species' low seed viability and poor natural regeneration, the study evaluated four types of propagules: root cuttings, semi hardwood and juvenile shoot cuttings, and coppice shoots from a Vegetative Multiplication Garden (VMG). Results demonstrated that root cuttings from mature trees (60-70 years old) achieved significant success with plantlet regeneration rates ranging from 41% to 74%. In shoot cuttings, ontogenic age was a critical factor; juvenile cuttings showed a markedly higher regenerative capacity (72%) compared to semi-hardwood cuttings (20%) when treated with optimal 5 mM IBA dose. Furthermore, a pilot trial with VMG-derived coppice shoots identified 5 mM IBA as the definitive protocol for maximizing frequency (56%), root number (7.8), and length (9.77). While non-auxin regulators like boric acid significantly improved root extension, IBA remained the superior orchestrator of rhizogenesis. These standardized protocols provide a reliable framework for mass multiplication of elite clonal stock, supporting both conservation and genetic improvement programmes for the species.

KEYWORD: Adventitious rooting, Candidate Plus Trees, Coppice shoot cuttings, Semi hardwood cuttings,

INTRODUCTION

Anogeissus acuminata (Roxb. ex DC.) Guillaumin & Perr., commonly known as Phasi, is a large deciduous tree belonging to the family Combretaceae, distributed across India (Odisha, Andhra Pradesh, Kerala), Myanmar, Cambodia, Laos, Thailand, and Vietnam. Owing to its pharmacological potency and diverse bioactive properties, *A. acuminata* holds significant medicinal and economic value (Navale *et al.*, 2016; Singh, 2021). Ethnomedicinal reports highlight its therapeutic applications in the treatment of diarrhoea, dysentery, wound healing, rheumatoid arthritis, tuberculosis, and various dermatological conditions (WOI, 1950; Shweta *et al.*, 2013; Singh *et al.*, 2016). Furthermore, several studies have demonstrated its promising antidiabetic activity in the management of diabetes mellitus (Rimando *et al.*, 1994; Hemamalini *et al.*, 2011). Notably, it has also been identified as a potential inhibitor of HIV-1 reverse transcriptase, underscoring its relevance in antiviral research (Manosroi *et al.*, 2011).

Beyond its pharmacological significance, *A. acuminata* is also valued for its exceptionally durable timber. The wood, recognized as one of the toughest among deciduous species, is widely utilized in the manufacture of tool handles, rafters, bobbins, wheel spokes, and furniture. Its mechanical strength and favorable working qualities have further embedded the species into the cultural and spiritual fabric of India, especially for employment in the world-renowned Ratha Yatra (Car Festival) at Puri, Odisha, where it is used to construct the massive chariot wheels of Lord Jagannatha. These wheels are traditionally fashioned from Phasi trees with an exploitable girth of 180 cm or greater (Udgata, 2011), withstand immense compressive and rotational loads. To meet the immediate demand for timber of such dimensions, systematic management practices have been initiated in select natural forest areas where the species occurs naturally. However, historical selective logging and progressive depletion of forest resources has severely constrained the availability of mature trees of the requisite size, rendering the sustainable supply of this culturally and economically significant timber increasingly difficult (Singh, 2014). This scenario underscores the urgent need for conservation, selective breeding, and genetic improvement of *A. acuminata*. To achieve these objectives, the development and standardization of efficient clonal propagation techniques are essential, as they provide a reliable means of producing genetically superior and uniform planting material. Such approaches would not only support the sustainable management of natural populations but also ensure the long-term availability of timber and medicinal resources derived from the species.

Although *A. acuminata* produces abundant seeds, the majority are empty, resulting in poor natural regeneration within forest ecosystems. Moreover, the seeds exhibit extremely low viability, further limiting successful recruitment. Consequently, nurseries

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rely primarily on stump (root-shoot) propagation to generate planting material. However, this method, being derived from sexual reproduction, cannot ensure genetic uniformity or the establishment of high-quality plantations comparable to clonal approaches. To date, no standardized clonal propagation protocol has been reported for the species, with the sole exception of an *in vitro* multiple-shoot induction technique developed from cotyledonary nodal segments (Rathore et al., 1993). Thus, the present study was undertaken to standardize clonal propagation procedures for *A. acuminata*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Four types of clonal propagules were employed: root cuttings, juvenile shoot cuttings derived from one-year-old seedlings, semi-hardwood shoot cuttings from mature trees, and coppiced hedge garden material.

Root cuttings were collected from nine identified candidate plus trees (CPTs) from three different regions in Odhisa (Table 1) and planted in 150 cc root trainers filled with a 1:1 mixture of coarse river sand and compost, following thorough washing in a mist chamber. No pre-treatment was applied to the 30 cuttings per CPT, which were planted in replicates of 10 under a Randomized Block Design. After four weeks of planting, plantlet production (% of root cuttings where both adventitious root and shoots were regenerated) was recorded.

In the second experiment, semi-hardwood shoot cuttings from mature trees (50–60 years old- C_1) and juvenile shoot cuttings derived from one-year-old seedlings (C_2) were subjected to basal dip treatments: distilled water (T_1), 5 mM indole-3-butyric acid (IBA; T_2), or 10 mM IBA (T_3) for 30 minutes. Cuttings were then planted in 150 cc root trainers filled with sterilized sand medium and maintained under controlled conditions in a mist chamber (temperature: $30\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$; relative humidity: $75\pm 5\%$). The experiment was arranged in a randomized block design with three replicates per treatment, each consisting of 20 cuttings. After four weeks, observations were recorded on adventitious rooting parameters, including rooting percentage, number of roots per cutting, and length of the longest root (cm).

Finally a pilot trial was conducted with coppice shoot cuttings collected from a Vegetative Multiplication Garden (VMG; hedge garden) established with clonal stock to enhance root induction through rejuvenation by regular hedging. Cuttings were subjected to 5 mM quick-dip treatments (30 s) with auxins—indole-3-acetic acid (IAA; T_2), indole-3-butyric acid (IBA; T_3), and naphthaleneacetic acid (NAA; T_4)—and non-auxin growth regulators—ascorbic acid (T_5), boric acid (T_6), pyridoxine (T_7), and thiamine (T_8). A water control (T_1) was also maintained. Treated cuttings were planted in root trainers filled with sterilized sand medium and maintained in a mist chamber under a randomized block design with three replicates per treatment, each consisting of 100 cuttings. After four weeks, observations were recorded on rooting percentage, number of roots per cutting, and length of the longest root (cm).

The data were statistically analyzed using analysis of variance (ANOVA). Prior to analysis, percentage data were transformed using the arcsine square root transformation to meet the assumptions of normality and homoscedasticity. Post-hoc comparisons were conducted using Tukey's HSD test ($p < 0.05$). Results are reported as untransformed means \pm standard error (SE).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Root cuttings

Plantlet regeneration from root cuttings, unlike stem cuttings, proceeds through a distinct two-step sequence: induction of adventitious shoots followed by the formation of a new root system at the shoot base. In this technique, roots are severed into segments, each capable of producing adventitious buds and roots, thereby regenerating into complete plants (Macdonald, 1990). The resulting plants are termed 'rootlings' (Hall et al., 1989; Snedden et al., 2010). This approach is particularly effective in tropical species with a natural propensity for root suckering. Root cuttings offer a simple, economical and reliable method of asexual propagation, which has been widely applied to hardy perennials with variable success (Eliasson, 1961; Uniyal et al., 1985; Hall et al., 1989; Ofori et al., 1996; Stenvall et al., 2004; Meunier et al., 2008; Snedden et al., 2010). Moreover, root cuttings provide advantages over stem cuttings for long-distance germplasm preservation, yielding higher multiplication coefficients without the need for sterile *in vitro* conditions (Zou et al., 2022).

The results from the present study clearly demonstrate that *A. acuminata* can be regenerated from root segments collected from mature, field grown trees. Remarkable success has been achieved in clonal plantlet production from mature trees (as old as 60-70 years) through root cuttings planting in mist chamber. The range of success was 41% to 74% (where both adventitious root and shoots were recorded) in different CPT groups (Fig. 1, 2). Despite highly significant variation among groups, which may be attributed to environmental and/or genetic differences, the procedure emerged as an efficient clonal method for mature ortets of *A. acuminata*.

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Juvenile vs. mature shoot cuttings

The rooting success was significantly influenced by both cutting type and IBA treatment in the second experiment. Furthermore, a significant interaction effect was observed between the two factors, indicating that the optimal IBA concentration for adventitious root induction is dependent on the specific cutting type utilized (Table 2).

IBA has been reported to be promotes adventitious root formation in various types of shoot cuttings of many tree species (Singh and Tomar, 2023a; Barthwal *et al.*, 2025). However, its stimulatory effect on root formation in cuttings may vary due to physiological, biological, and anatomical differences among species (Ansari and Singh 2008; Hartmann *et al.* 2011). Simple main effects analysis demonstrated that for both cutting types, the application of IBA significantly enhanced rooting compared to the control (Fig. 3) For Semi hardwood cutting (C_1), the highest rooting percentage was achieved at 5 mM IBA (20.0 %), which was significantly higher than the 14.33% observed at 10 mM IBA. Cuttings in the control group failed to initiate any roots. A similar trend was observed for Juvenile cutting (C_2), which exhibited a markedly higher overall regenerative capacity. The 5 mM IBA treatment again proved most effective, yielding a maximum rooting percentage of 72.0 %. This represented a significant increase over both the 10 mM IBA treatment (58.0%) and the control (19.67%). The magnitude of response to IBA was notably greater in C_2 ; the transition from control to the optimal 5 mM IBA dose resulted in a 52.3% absolute increase in rooting success, compared to a 20.0% increase in C_1 . These results suggest that while 5 mM IBA is the optimal concentration across both types, C_2 possesses a significantly higher sensitivity and potential for hormone-induced rhizogenesis.

The significant enhancement of rooting following the exogenous application of Indole-3-butyric acid (IBA) underscores its critical role in triggering the transition of quiescent cells into active root primordia. Our results demonstrate a clear dose-response relationship, where 5 mM IBA served as the optimal concentration for both cutting types. However, the observed decline in rooting percentage at the higher concentration of 10 mM IBA suggests a supra-optimal hormonal effect. The present findings corroborate earlier reports indicating that moderate concentrations of exogenous IBA effectively stimulate adventitious rhizogenesis, whereas supra-optimal levels exert inhibitory effects on root development and may induce phytotoxicity in shoot cuttings (Singh *et al.*, 2004; Singh *et al.*, 2006; Piñon *et al.*, 2023; Çetin and Baş, 2025).

The stark contrast in regenerative capacity between the two cutting types—where the control group of C_2 outperformed the optimal treatment of Type 1—suggests that ontogenetic age and/or carbohydrate reserves within the cutting tissue may be as critical as hormonal stimulation (Fig. 4). The fact that C_1 cuttings completely failed to root without IBA treatment highlights a severe endogenous auxin deficiency or a high level of rooting inhibitors that only the 5 mM dose could partially overcome.

The potential for adventitious rhizogenesis, and consequently the ease of clonal propagation, declines with increasing tree age (Francelet, 1979). Juvenile plants, although unresponsive to floral induction under external or internal stimuli, exhibit maximal regenerative capacity, with tissues and organs readily forming adventitious roots, shoots, or both (Singh and Tomar, 2023a). In most cases, cuttings derived from juvenile seedlings (softwood) consistently outperform semi-hardwood cuttings from mature trees in root induction. This superiority is attributed to higher physiological activity, reduced lignification, and a greater responsiveness of juvenile tissues to exogenous rooting hormones. In contrast, cloning at the mature stage—when desirable traits are fully expressed—remains challenging in many tree species (Singh *et al.*, 2003, Singh and Barthwal, 2022). In the present investigation, juvenile shoot cuttings from one-year-old seedlings demonstrated significantly higher adventitious rooting compared to semi-hardwood cuttings from mature trees. Comparable findings have been reported in several rooting-recalcitrant forestry species (Swamy *et al.*, 2002; Ansari and Singh, 2003; Husen and Pal, 2007; Singh and Ansari, 2014; Kumar *et al.*, 2022).

Coppice shoot cuttings

In the third experiment, the experimental treatments exerted a highly significant influence on all measured parameters of adventitious root formation (Table 3). T_3 (5 mM IBA) was identified as the optimal protocol, exhibiting superior performance in rooting percentage (56.00%), root multiplication (7.83 roots per cutting), and longitudinal root extension (9.77 cm). The magnitude of this response suggests that the specific conditions within T_3 may provide a synergistic environment for both the induction and elongation phases of root development (Fig. 5).

Among plant growth regulators, auxin is widely recognized as the central orchestrator of adventitious root formation, acting as the primary regulator and a pivotal mediator of hormonal crosstalk during this process (Druege *et al.*, 2019; Lakehal and Bellini, 2019; Lakehal *et al.*, 2020).

Exogenous application of auxins such as indole-3-acetic acid (IAA), indole-3-butyric acid (IBA), and naphthaleneacetic acid (NAA) has been shown to stimulate adventitious rhizogenesis in shoot cuttings across diverse species (Blakesly *et al.*, 1991). In addition to auxins, several non-auxin compounds—including ascorbic acid, boric acid, pyridoxine, and thiamine—play critical roles as cofactors and metabolic regulators that enhance rooting, particularly in recalcitrant or difficult-to-root tree species (Hati *et al.*, 1990; Palanisamy *et al.*, 1998; Ansari *et al.*, 2001; Singh *et al.*, 2005; Singh and Tomar, 2023b). These compounds generally exert their effects by improving carbohydrate metabolism, strengthening antioxidant defense systems to mitigate stress, and promoting synergistic interactions with auxins, thereby facilitating both root initiation and elongation.

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A comparative analysis of the secondary treatments reveals a divergence between rooting initiation and subsequent growth quality. Overall, the effectiveness of auxins in promoting adventitious rhizogenesis in coppice shoot cuttings of *Anogeissus acuminata* followed the order IBA > NAA > IAA. This hierarchy of response is consistent with earlier findings in *Tectona grandis* (teak), where IBA proved superior to other auxins in stimulating root induction (Ansari and Singh, 2003). While NAA (T₄) achieved the second-highest rooting frequency (26.00%), it yielded significantly shorter roots (2.10 cm) compared to Boric acid-T₆ (4.43 cm). This indicates that although the induction stimulus in NAA was relatively effective, it may not have supported the physiological requirements for sustained cell division in the root apical meristem as effectively as Boric acid. Furthermore, the lack of significant differentiation between Treatments- Pyridoxine (T₇), Thiamine (T₈), and the control (T₁) across several metrics suggests that these protocols failed to surpass the endogenous threshold required for enhanced rhizogenesis. This study highlights the critical role of treatment selection in optimizing rooting architecture. Application of 5 mM IBA is recommended as the definitive protocol for maximizing both the quantity and vigor of the root system.

Vegetative Multiplication Gardens (VMGs) and hedge orchards are specialized mother plant blocks established to provide high-quality, juvenile propagules for large-scale clonal propagation (Singh et al., 2003). By maintaining donor plants in a permanently juvenile or “hedged” state, these systems effectively circumvent the age-related decline in rooting capacity typically observed in mature trees.

The efficiency of such gardens, however, depends critically on appropriate management practices, particularly the optimization of hedging prescriptions, as demonstrated in species such as *Tectona grandis* (Singh et al., 2006). In the present investigation, the profuse root induction observed in coppice shoot cuttings derived from VMGs underscores the importance of proper stockplant management and the standardization of hedging schedules to ensure a perpetual supply of rejuvenated propagules, thereby facilitating mass multiplication of *A. acuminata*.

CONCLUSIONS

The study successfully standardizes a multi-pronged clonal propagation framework for *Anogeissus acuminata*, effectively overcoming the barriers of poor seed viability and natural regeneration. A significant breakthrough is the high success rate (up to 74%) in regenerating plantlets from root cuttings of mature trees, providing a reliable method for preserving aged germplasm. Furthermore, the research confirms that juvenility maintenance through hedge orchards (VMGs) and treatment with 5 mM IBA are the most effective strategies for mass-producing high-quality, uniform planting material.

Table 1. Details of the CPTs employed in root cutting trial.

CPT group	CPT Code	Division	Range	Latitude	Longitude	Altitude (m)
1	ODSAT01	Satkosia	Jillinda	N 20°31'48.1”	E 84°50'59.9”	74
	ODSAT02	Satkosia	Jillinda	N 20°31'55.2”	E 84°50'53.2”	73
	ODSAT08	Satkosia	Tikripara	N 20°33'49.9”	E 84°49'22.4”	69
2	ODSAT05	Boudh	Kankai	N 20°36'45.6”	E 84°43'44.3”	78
	ODSAT06	Boudh	Kankai	N 20°36'41.8”	E 84°43'45.2”	74
	ODSAT07	Boudh	Kankai	N 20°36'45.7”	E 84°43'44.7”	78
3	ODNAY16	Nayagarh	Gania	N 20°27.805'	E 84°58.83'	115
	ODNAY18	Nayagarh	Gania	N 20°27.10'	E 84°59.543'	61
	ODNAY19	Nayagarh	Gania	N 20°26.709'	E 84°59.995'	126

Table 2. Details of the CPTs employed in root cutting trial

Cutting type	Treatments		
	Control	5 mM IBA	10 mM IBA
Type 1	0.00±0.00 ^c	20.00±1.00 ^a	14.33±1.45 ^b
Type 2	19.67±1.20 ^c	72.00±1.15 ^a	58.00±1.17 ^b

Table 3. Details of the CPTs employed in root cutting trial.

Treatment	Rooting (%) ¹	Root Number	Root Length (cm)
Control	4.33 ± 0.33 ^e	1.00 ± 0.00 ^d	3.31 ± 0.06 ^c
IAA	19.00 ± 1.15 ^{bc}	1.80 ± 0.06 ^c	2.53 ± 0.09 ^d
IBA	56.00 ± 2.31 ^a	7.83 ± 0.09 ^a	9.77 ± 0.12 ^a
NAA	26.00 ± 1.15 ^b	2.47 ± 0.03 ^b	2.10 ± 0.06 ^{de}
Ascorbic acid	21.00 ± 0.58 ^{be}	0.97 ± 0.03 ^d	1.80 ± 0.12 ^e

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Boric acid	16.00 ± 1.15 ^c	3.03 ± 0.09 ^b	4.43 ± 0.12 ^b
Pyridoxine	12.00 ± 0.58 ^{cd}	1.00 ± 0.00 ^d	1.90 ± 0.06 ^e
Thiamine	10.00 ± 1.15 ^d	1.00 ± 0.09 ^d	1.80 ± 0.12 ^e

¹ Statistical analysis for rooting (%) was performed on arcsine square root transformed data; however, original (untransformed) means are presented for clarity.

Fig. 1. Rooting variation in root cuttings from CPTs

Fig. 2. Success in propagation through root cuttings; in 60-70 year trees

Fig. 3. Effect of IBA treatment on adventitious rooting in shoot cuttings

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Fig. 4. Adventitious rooting as influenced by cutting type

Fig. 5. 5 mM IBA induced luxuriant rooting in coppice shoot cuttings

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